

ISic0298

Dedication to the Genius of the city of Catania

Language

Type

Material

Object

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Serena Agodi,system,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2016.05.13

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di
Catania, inventory 2

Physical Description

A tablet of white marble, smooth on the sides and the reverse, with the remains of a raised border (a moulding?) on the right side. The front face is lightly convex.

Dimensions

Height 62 cm

Width 58 cm

Depth 4.5-6.0 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: 60-80 mm

Line 2-4: 40-60 mm

Line 5-7: 50-70 mm

Interlineation

Line line1 to line1 : mm

Text

1. Vernantibus
2. saeculis ddd(ominorum) nnn(ostrorum)
3. Genio splendidae ur
4. bis Catinae
5. Facundus Porfyrius Mynatidius v(ir) c(larissimus) ·
7. cons(ularis) · eiusdem

Apparatus

Translation (en)

At the dawn of the new age of our threefold lordship, (dedicated) to the Genius of the splendid city

of Catania. Facundus Porfyrius Mynatidius, vir clarissimus, consular governor of the same (city?)

(set this up).

Translation (it)

Nel rifiorire dell'era dei nostri tre signori, al genio della splendida città di Catania Facundio

Porfirio Munatidio, senatore (vir clarissimus) governatore consolare della stessa (città?) (dedicò).

Commentary

The text (on imported marble) would have been fixed to the base of a statue of the Genius of the city of Catania, probably erected on the stage-building of the theatre. The Genius was the protective spirit of a person or a thing. Dedications to the Genius of the Emperor were common, but also to cities (e.g. both a statue and temple of the Genius of the city of Lilybaeum = Marsala are mentioned in other inscriptions). Facundus Porfyrius is not otherwise known. The precise significance of 'cons eiusdem' in line 7 is extensively debated and several alternatives have been suggested: the most likely interpretation is 'consularis eiusdem', signifying consularis of the same city, i.e. Catania, and so by extension / implication the province of Sicily.

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Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. *Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum.* Berlin. At 10.7014 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650756>)

1888-. *L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1959.0022

Korhonen, K. 2004. *Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione.* Helsinki. At 7

Dessau, H. 1892-1916. *Inscriptiones Latinae Selectae*. Berlin. At 3778
Holm, A. 1925. *Catania antica*. Catania. At 43-44
Manganaro, G. 1958-1959. Iscrizioni latine e greche di Catania tardo-imperiale. *Archivio Storico per la Sicilia Orientale*. ser.4 vol.11-12: 5-30. At 5-10 fig.1
Wilson, R.J.A. 1990. *Sicily under the Roman Empire: the archaeology of a Roman province, 36 B.C. - A.D. 535*. Warminster. At 187 fig.156.b
Manganaro, G. 1993. Greco nei pagi e latino nelle città della Sicilia romana tra I e VI sec. d.C.. In Calbi, A., Donati, A., Poma, G.(eds.), *l'epigrafia del villaggio*. Faenza. pp. 543-594. At 560, 583 fig.19

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Photograph of front face by J. Prag